

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ БЛОКА “СТРАТЕГИИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ” УЧЕБНОЙ ПРОГРАММЫ ПО ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОМУ ПРЕДМЕТУ В СРЕДНИХ ШКОЛАХ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА НА ОСНОВЕ “СИСТЕМНО-СТРУКТУРНОГО” ПОДХОДА

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INTERPRETATION OF THE ELEMENTS OF THE "TEACHING STRATEGIES" BLOCK OF THE TECHNOLOGY SUBJECT CURRICULUM IN AZERBAIJAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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Аннотация

В статье подчеркивается, что реформа учебной программы обусловлена необходимостью обеспечить адекватность внедрения образования в Азербайджане требованиям 21 века, воспитать творческую, саморазвивающуюся личность, а также содержанием способностей, которые должны быть преобразованы в предмет нового образования. показан студент, получивший общее образование.

Значимость обращения преподавателя к "системно-структурному" подходу в исследовательской работе как при ознакомлении с сутью "общеобразовательной программы", так и в его практической деятельности, связанной с ее реализацией, соответствие предметно-ориентированной учебной программы содержанию научной области и ее совершенная система понятий, непосредственно связанных с этими понятиями. Он притягивается к центру внимания, направленного на его поглощение.

В статье рассматриваются 1) принципы педагогического процесса, 2) планирование обучения по предмету, 3) формы и методы, используемые при организации обучения, 4) стандарты содержания, которые включены в блок "Стратегии обучения" формы "Блок-схема" структуры учебного процесса. в учебной программе по предмету "Технология" на уровне общего образования представлена интерпретация обобщений, сделанных адекватно собранным фактическим данным, на основе диалектического подхода "система-структура"., которая направлена на раскрытие природы упомянутых подсистем, чтобы принести пользу преподавателю на желаемом уровне от интерпретации и инструктивных указаний при организации и управлении реальным педагогическим процессом.

Abstract

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education in Azerbaijan to the demands of the 21st century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities that must be transformed into the subject of a student who has completed his general education is shown.

The significance of the educator's reference to the "system-structure" approach in the research work both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the "General Education Program" and in his practical activities related to its implementation, the relevance of subject-oriented curriculum to the content of the science field, and its perfect system of concepts, directly related to these concepts. It is drawn to the center of attention directed to its absorption.

In the article, 1) principles of the pedagogical process, 2) planning of training in the subject, 3) forms and methods used in the organization of training, 4) content standards, which are included in the "Teaching strategies" block of the "block-scheme" form of the structure of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level. An interpretation of the generalizations made adequately to the collected evidence is presented based on the "system-structure" dialectical approach, which aims to reveal the nature of the mentioned sub-systems in order to

benefit the educator at the desired level from the interpretation and instructional instructions in the organization and management of the real pedagogical process.

Ключевые слова: Образовательная программа; учебный план; предметная программа; форма учебной программы "блок-схема"; стратегии обучения; полнота; равные возможности; благоприятная среда; учебный блок; учебная ситуация; исследовательский вопрос; мотивация; обмен информацией; рефлексия; деловые формы; работа с группами; творческое применение.

Keywords: Educational program; curriculum; subject curriculum; "block-scheme" form of the curriculum; learning strategies; completeness; equal opportunities; supportive environment; teaching unit; teaching situation; research question; motivation; information exchange; reflection; business forms; work with groups; creative application.

Relevance of the research topic.

Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of the Technology subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the teaching process of Informatics.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage of it in adequate directions. On the basis of our scientific observations conducted over the last ten years (at the stage of applying a new approach to the philosophy of general education in Azerbaijan), we have come to the conclusion that in the process of using the subject curricula (including the Technology subject curriculum), the basis of the errors manifested in the activities of the educators, along with a number of reasons, is also the subject the essence of the curriculum is not sufficiently understood by these subjects. Based on our experience of scientific activity, we claim that the "system-structure" approach (the idea of L. Bertalanf, which is the basis of system analysis[14;8]) is the understanding of any objective reality (material or spiritual), it is the most reliable dialectical method of getting to its essence, in other words, the way of spiritual exploration (It is essentially a form of cognitive action). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the Technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application ways. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues that lead to the solution of the problem that created the basis for the manifestation of the error explained above - "The formulation of the Technology subject curriculum in Azerbaijan secondary schools as "Interpretation of the elements of the "Teaching strategies" block based on the "system-structure" approach" and its actual research we claim to be the subject. it is a way of spiritual awakening (It is essentially a form of cognitive movement). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the Technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application ways. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues that lead to the solution of the problem that created the basis for the manifestation of the error explained above - "The formulation of the Technology subject curriculum in Azerbaijan secondary schools as "Interpretation of the elements of

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Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials.

It is known that "in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality" [15; 16] and there is also the fact that education cannot exist outside the realities of the changing world [11].

Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on activity, the need to understand and abilities.

Despite what has been said, a student who has completed general education should be able to: analyze the texts of different styles and genres that he listens to and reads, and convey their content to someone else in a concise and partly extensive form; to use monologue and dialogue forms of speech; preparing a plan, thesis, overview, project, opinion; to logically justify their ideas through examples and evidence, to summarize the main points expressed in different ideas; perform calculations and programming, use mathematical language, build algorithms, make assumptions; to use the methods and means of observation, measurement, calculation, experiment, evaluation to understand the surrounding world; to explain the nature of the basic regularities in nature and their interrelation; various facts, to compare, classify and present reasoning and evidence; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language and so on. categorize and present; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language and so on. categorize and present; independently perform tasks that require creativity in the training process; to use different sources of information to perform training tasks; to consciously determine one's capabilities, inclination and interest, to demonstrate voluntary and involuntary qualities; to evaluate the results of his work; to follow public behavior, as well as relevant safety and medical-hygiene rules, healthy lifestyle norms; to demonstrate that he has national, moral, legal, aesthetic values, citizenship position, and leadership qualities; to work together in solving problems, to evaluate the performance of oneself and others in the collective work process; to communicate in a foreign language and so on.

The listed skills of the student who has completed his general education - the general learning results are formed as a synthesis, dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects taught in general education schools.

"Revealing the child's creative abilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education" [7; 290-292]. There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of the subjects are expressed in the "Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan" in the following content:

- ensures that students are taught the basics of science, inculcated the necessary knowledge, skills and habits, prepare them for life and work;

- enables physical and intellectual development of students, acquisition of necessary knowledge, formation of civic thinking based on healthy lifestyle and civilized values, inculcation of respect for national and worldly values, determination of rights and responsibilities in front of family, society, state and environment [2; 21-23].

Based on the official state documents, we can say the opinion that "the content of general education subjects is divided into different levels of education and aims at the following iyearxic goals":

- to overcome reading, writing and calculation skills in primary education, to form basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic and artistic taste and other characteristics;

- oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization, the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events to provide the ability to evaluate and determine their own future directions of action;

- realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, acquiring the basics of economic knowledge, communicating in one or more foreign languages, etc. provide (see [2] for more information).

In the mentioned system of knowledge, skills and habits, what is achieved in the teaching of the subject of Technology is included as a component. In accordance with the framework document "Concept of general education in the Republic of Azerbaijan (National Curriculum)", the tasks of the subject "Technology" in secondary schools are defined as follows:

At the primary education level, students are trained in comparison and sorting, primary processing, self-service and cooperative habits, simple design,

layout, modeling, design, living nature service skills, measurement, proportion, symmetry and other geometric concepts, and the ability to perform simple constructions and creative works. Vaccination is provided.

Improving technological and applied skills by developing the activities intended for the performance of functional tasks at the level of secondary education, implementing non-simple technological processes, forming creative technical thinking, expanding students' opportunities to use modern information technologies, guiding them to choose a profession, hard work and creativity education in the spirit is ensured. [1].

Due to our adequate generalization to our subjective meaning, it is of particular importance that the subject teacher (as well as the teacher who teaches the subject of Technology) honestly knows the tasks set before the general education (the expected general results). This is necessary for the activity related to the educational process to be put into a result-oriented system.

As is known, the goal is a system-creative component in all processes, as well as training-activity. At the same time, in order for the goal to become actionable (otherwise the result will not be produced), it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on what strategy, based on what evaluation mechanisms. "The new necessary minimum of training at the levels of general education, the knowledge threshold, the general training results for the subject and the training results that will be obtained in advance of the acquired skills at individual levels of general education (subsystems of the implementation system of general education) (which these results are in the expected general results is included as components - italics are ours) is considered one of the most important problems of education" [12; 71].

As is known, the teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what specific features this model has. This model incorporates the superior merits of traditional models (it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process.

Based on what we have said, it can be concluded that the Technology curriculum is a set of documents that reflects all the activities aimed at achieving the general learning outcomes by setting the main goals of informatics training in secondary schools and is directed to the capabilities and needs of each student. It is intended for teachers, school leaders, textbook authors, parents and the general public. Informatics subject curriculum forms the basis of the rules to be prepared in the form of appropriate guidelines for the preparation of textbooks and teaching aids, planning of

teaching materials, determination of teaching methods and implementation of teacher training.

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structure" approach both in getting to know the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, which the analysis of research materials and our work experience brings us to this conclusion.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their interaction, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it for different levels of education in accordance with state education standards [9; 106-107]. The educational program includes the curriculum, curricula for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies [8; 173]. Listed are complete subsystems of the Education program.

The technology subject curriculum: 1) maintains a balanced and comprehensive approach that involves the study of various skills; 2) makes it possible to reach the level of content standards by using active methods of training; 3) involves the constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; 4) ensures that students are involved in training, prepared for continuous education and encouraged; 5) provides for the use of modern technologies while studying, evaluating the knowledge, and increasing the literacy of students; 6) has appropriate training resources and administrative support [4;158-161]. The block diagram form of the structure of the mentioned curriculum can be drawn as follows [8; 38] (see Scheme 1):

Scheme 1

The "Teaching strategies" block covers the forms, methods and techniques used by the teacher in the teaching process. It should be noted that until this time, the concept of "teaching strategies" was not used in the Azerbaijani pedagogical literature. However, recently, during the period of educational reform, the concept of "educational strategy" began to be addressed when preparing subject curricula [5; 280]. The development of the concept of learning strategies in new subject curricula and its more efficient use in the organization of the pedagogical process requires, first of all, the explanation of education as one of the main pedagogical concepts in terms of modern requirements. The "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education" stipulates that education is systematized (according to the interests of the state, society, individual - italics are ours) knowledge, skills, is the process of acquiring habits and its result. [2; 6]. Scientific sources emphasize that education should be treated not only as a result or just a process, but as a way of expression with broader shades of meaning. "Especially the personality-oriented nature of education requires to approach it from several positions: education is a value; education is a system; education is a process; education is the result". [13; 115]. We completely agree with this idea.

Among the elements contained in the "Teaching strategies" block, "Teaching planning by subject" has a special place. Creating annual planning is the most important task facing educators. Planning is the direction of action of teachers to determine the main goals and achieve them. The annual planning shows when and in what order the teaching unit will teach.

The main documents used in the annual planning process are: content standards; assessment standards; education plan; textbook; methodological tool for the teacher. In particular, let's emphasize that during the preparation of the calendar plan, the weeks of the school year, important events that will take place in the school year (historical days), the name of the study units and the subjects included in them are determined. The content standards (sub-standards) to be realized through each educational unit and topic are selected, the resources to be used are determined, and the time

allotted for each topic is noted. Based on the model annual planning, the teacher individually prepares a daily or weekly lesson plan. [5; 281]

According to the descriptive scheme of the curriculum of the technology subject, in the "Education strategies" block, the "element acting as a central link" is the form and methods (methods) of the organization of training.

Despite the fact that the clear understanding of the concept of "Teaching method", which is one of the important elements of the "Teaching strategies" system, and the discovery of its essence have important theoretical and practical importance, the debates among didacts in this direction have been going on for a long time [11]. In our opinion, the training method is a system of rules aimed at solving the educational, educational and developmental tasks set in the training process, determined by the principles derived from the regularities of training, and ensuring the dialectical unity of the activities of teachers and students (a component of the training process). Since the standards are result-oriented and student-oriented, it is considered appropriate to use active training methods in their implementation [5; 286-2875]:

Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in secondary schools is the lesson. The improvement of educational material, which contains a part of human social experience, and educational methods aimed at its mastery, conditions the modernization of their form of existence (educational material and methods for the lesson act together in the place of content) (turning into a suitable way of existence) (such is the dialectical dependence between form and content). Therefore, in addition to "traditional lesson", "modern lesson", "developing lesson", "problematic lesson", "phased lesson", "synthetic lesson", "active lesson" etc. Concepts reflecting the quality characteristics of the lesson were used from time to time, and scientific comments were given to them. With intensive pedagogical, psychological and methodological researches, the "modern lesson" model was created and the era (the current century,

The word "modern" in the sense of "modern lesson" has a unique heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the successes of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, they usually distinguish two aspects that are organically connected with each other. Often, when they say modern lesson, they understand it only as raising the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, modernizing it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific and theoretical level. This is without a doubt. However, it would be one-sided to explain the meaning of the modern lesson only in this root. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" characterizes the lesson. This is true both from a psychological and pedagogical point of view, as well as from a linguistic point of view. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - it is built with new pedagogical thinking dimensions [7; 36-37]

Stationary or problematic manifestation can do. Therefore, depending on the stationarity or problem, the student's thought movement is reproductive or productive. In the forms of organization of training, the content of the training material and the methods of action adequate to it appear in the place of the content. Therefore, the substructures of the forms of organization of training and their relationship remain in the monopoly of the relationship between the student's analytical and heuristic activities. The basis of the pedagogical (external), mental (internal) and methodical inter-structural relations of the organizational form is also the relation between the students' analytical and heuristic activities. The relationship between the degree of pedagogical influence in the training process and the student's internal activity and independence reflects the nature of his (student's) activity. At present, the approach to this process as a field of activity aimed at developing the human personality has begun to prevail. This did not remain unaffected by the forms of education, views on its organization, and directions for improvement. In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's emphasize that "modern lesson" is used as a synonym for the concept of "active lesson", which is an organizational form of active (interactive) training.

The structure of the active lesson reminds of the stages of the research process (the main shade of the learning process is research). In an active lesson, new information is obtained through the student himself (as a result of research). The stage of application in an active lesson is creative in nature. One of the special stages of the active lesson is the reflection stage. As a result of reflection, the student understands the main stages of his research activity.

Learning success is determined not only by the student's ability to learn, overall abilities, etc., but also by learning motivation. In other words, for him to "read well", along with all other conditions, it is necessary to form learning motivation.

Motivation is an important component in an active lesson - it is a process that activates the thinking process and stimulates the cognitive activity of students..

Motivation should be consistent with the learning outcomes of the lesson. Before building the motivation, "Substandards" and then "Learning outcomes of the lesson" should be defined. The research question arises as a result of the motivation. Motivation can be short and gradual. A short motivation consists of only one research question.

The following criteria are used to evaluate motivation: 1) Appropriateness of motivation; 2) The emergence of problems and various assumptions as a result of motivation; 3) Conciseness of motivation, implementation in a short time; 4) The teacher spends little time and effort on its preparation; 5) Comprehension by children with moderate difficulty (considering their age and knowledge level).

"Information exchange" which is one of the concluding stages of the active lesson its purpose is to introduce all students to new facts and findings. Information sharing can only be effective if the class is focused on active listening and feedback.

"Discussion and organization of information" The next step is to systematize knowledge based on new facts and uncovering the key relationship to answer the research question. It is clear that the material that the teacher has to work with is detailed. He must try to connect these scattered facts to discover the main unifying idea and pattern. In that time period, comparison, analysis and synthesis are used. Let us emphasize that the choice here depends on the content of the material and the purpose of the research.

"Deriving conclusions, justifying generalization" is one of the structural elements of the lesson. After generalization, the idea formed should be compared with the research question (Does it answer this question?) and with the initial hypotheses (Are any of these correct?).

In the application of the technology curriculum, daily planning for each active lesson system is also an element to be focused on. It is useful to include the following in daily planning: 1) Determine the expected results of the lesson (determine the learning results of the lesson based on the sub-standard); 2) Determine what conclusions (generalizations) the students will come to at the end of the lesson; 3) Preparing the motivation of the lesson (creating a problem situation, choosing the type of motivation, setting the research question correctly); 4) Identify the sources of knowledge used to gather new knowledge during research; 5) To prepare research tasks that can lead to certain expected results; 6) Determine research methods; 7) Prepare the necessary materials and worksheets, determine the presentation form of the research; 8) To express guiding questions used during the discussion; 9) Systematization of information (scheme, formula, graph, table, project, etc.); 10) To prepare additional information and tasks, taking into account the assumed new results; 11) Determine the time for each stage of the lesson; 12) preparing tasks for the creative application stage; 13) Choosing the evaluation form (method), defining the criteria; 14)

Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of the teacher and students; 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286] defining criteria; 14) Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of the teacher and students; 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286] defining criteria; 14) Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of the teacher and students; 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286]

Individual, pair, large and small group work is included among the forms of organization of students' educational activities (work forms) included in the "Teaching strategies" block. The teacher's and students' adherence to certain rules during the organization of group work had a positive effect on the effectiveness of the work. The following are attributed by students to the organizational aspect of group work: 1) Correctly dividing the tasks of group members; 2) Identifying group leaders correctly; 3) Using time efficiently. Behavioral aspects of group work are attributed by students: 1) Being active during group work; 2) Fulfill the obligation and take responsibility for one's own behavior; 3) Listen carefully to each other; 3) Working together, cooperating, helping each other, to support; 4) Collectively, help the group to successfully achieve its goals; 5) To express one's point of view; 6) Respect each other's ideas; 7) To confirm one's thoughts and ideas with knowledge (facts); 8) To help create an environment of good relations, not to allow personal criticism, negative comments and insults; 9) Avoid conflict, compete in the positive sense of the word; 10) Looking for compromise ways when solving the problem; 11) Do not allow extraneous conversations, talk on the topic given by the teacher; 12) Observing discipline during work; 13) To obey the rules of group work. (For more information, see [10; 15]). not to allow negative comments and insults; 9) Avoid conflict, compete in the positive sense of the word; 10) Looking for compromise ways when solving the problem; 11) Do not allow extraneous conversations, talk on the topic given by the teacher; 12) Observing discipline during work; 13) To obey the rules of group work. (For more information, see [10; 15]). not to allow negative comments and insults; 9) Avoid conflict, compete in the positive sense of the word; 10) Looking for compromise ways when solving the problem; 11) Do not allow extraneous conversations, talk on the topic given by the teacher; 12) Observing discipline during work; 13) To obey the rules of group work. (For more information, see [10; 15]).

It is useful for the teacher, which is the main component of active/interactive learning, which we consider as a sub-system of the perfect training system, and which gives priority to constructivism and cooperativism, in the implementation of the guiding position as a specific function, to expect the rules of facilitation. The following rules are expected for the purpose of inciting thought: 1) At the motivation stage, involving students in determining the topic of the lesson; 2) To include in the lesson tasks that develop

students' logical, critical, creative thinking and scientific-research habits; 3) Using more open questions; 4) Comparing and contrasting concrete material during facilitation, to use methods of analogy; 5) Using guiding questions that are close in meaning; 6) Not to express the word or idea that the participant (student) could say instead; 7) Determine the main idea contained in the material and work on students' generalization skills; 8) Avoid formal listening of the students' answers, summarize the main ideas of the students; 9) To clarify students' answers during facilitation. [10; 255]

Note that the facilitycooperation of teachers and students, mutual respect and trust of teachers and students, acceptance of students as they are and their constant support by the teacher; confidence in students' abilities, stimulation of thinking; it is based on the creation of learning stimulus and motivation in students, their adaptation to the classroom environment, and the special sensitive attitude of the teacher.[15]

Interpretation of content standards is one of the important elements included in the "Teaching strategies" block. It is emphasized in scientific sources that the content standard is the state requirement set for the level of knowledge and skills of the student [5; 468].

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity. The content standards of this or that subject are systematized by classes and represented by the content line. It is attributed to the functions of the sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work. 1) The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, which was formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum (especially the Technology subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods), was brought to the attention of the researchers; 2) The discovery of the essence of the Technology subject curriculum in Azerbaijan secondary schools and its The solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution of the problem of the application of the application in the optimal version - "Interpretation of the elements of the "Education strategies" block based on the "system-structure" approach in Azerbaijan secondary schools" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work.

We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of uncovering the essence of this or that subject curriculum (as well as the Technology subject curriculum) applied at the general education level and its application in the optimal version - "system- the

presentation of the interpretation based on the "structural approach" will have a positive effect on the formation of the environment for the elimination of errors manifested in the activities of educators in the application of the Technology subject curriculum.

The result.

1) The level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of benefiting from it in adequate directions. 2) In the application of any subject curriculum (as well as the Technology subject curriculum) at the general education level, making mistakes in the activities of educators has a negative effect on the level of efficiency of the teaching process of this subject. affect; 3) In the process of using the technology subject curriculum, the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of practical educators is based not only on reasons, but also on the lack of honest enough understanding of its essence by these subjects; .4) "system-structure" approach to understanding any existing, it is the most reliable dialectical method of getting to the essence; 5) The dialectical method of "system-structure" approach was not used in theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of IT curriculum and the determination of its application methods; 6) One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the technology subject curriculum and the determination of the ways of its application is "Interpretation of the elements of the "Teaching strategies" block of the technology subject curriculum in Azerbaijan secondary schools based on the "system-structure" approach " and our research summary presented in this direction benefits the teaching process of this or that subject.

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